

INNOVATIVE TRENDS AND TECHNOLOGIES ON IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF ADVANCED TRAINING OF ADMINISTRATIVE AND PEDAGOGICAL STAFF OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Aliev Islambek Tursinbayevich

associate professor, Ph.D. Renaissance University of Education

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14505072>

In the conditions of strong increasing competition in the world market, it is important to further improve the efficiency of the personnel training system by improving the quality of education and scientific potential in ensuring the economic development of the country. At the same time, radical improvement of the activities of higher educational institutions in the field of economics and finance, the establishment of its effective management system, the introduction of the latest pedagogical technologies in the educational process, the organization of scientific activity based on world standards, further improvement of their place in international rankings, the wide involvement of scientific and pedagogical personnel with advanced foreign experience are the basis for the training of competitive personnel for the country's economic and financial systems.

The article is devoted to the study of current issues of training highly qualified teaching staff for the Republic of Uzbekistan, based on modern requirements of the time. The purpose of the article is to determine the impact of the quality of training of teaching staff on the progressive development of Uzbekistan.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan enshrines the right of citizens to receive quality education, in this regard, a number of legal acts aimed at reforming the educational system were adopted. As a result, of the implementation of the Law "On Education", the National Program for Personnel Training, which received international recognition, the structure of education has completely changed, the material and technical base of educational institutions has been strengthened, including the system of advanced training of teaching staff has completely changed.

Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated 21.06.2024 N PP-231 "On additional measures to improve the system of continuous professional development of employees of preschool and school education organizations" is intended to raise work in this area to a new level. It provides for a radical change in the structure of the institute for advanced training of teachers. Modern requirements for a teacher include knowledge of the norms of legislation, the latest achievements in the field of theory, scientific and applied research in the taught discipline, as well as modern methods of organizing the educational process. The functioning of permanent courses for retraining and advanced training of management and teaching staff of universities is subordinated to these goals. [1].

The new system of retraining and advanced training of teaching staff of universities in Uzbekistan provides for a fundamental change in the structure of the institute for advanced training of teachers and is designed to raise work in this area to a new level. Regular improvement of the pedagogical and professional level of professorial and teaching staff of universities, their in-depth study of legislative norms, the latest achievements in the field of theory, applied research, technological progress and innovation, as well as modern methods of

organizing the educational process will undoubtedly contribute to improving the quality of training highly qualified specialists. [2].

Training courses are conducted by leading trainers and teachers trained in new innovative technologies. The results of module tests, pedagogical (qualification) practice, defense of the final project work according to the established criteria, and indicators of professional activity over the past 3 years are registered in the electronic system. Monitoring of the learners' educational activity is carried out on the basis of a 100-point rating system. Each learner has an electronic record book and a portfolio, which includes materials reflecting his achievements during the course, certification results, post-course pedagogical activity, as well as educational resources intended for learners.

Learners of the course who have fully mastered the educational programs for retraining and advanced training and successfully passed the certification are issued certificates. A modern electronic online library has been created, including information and reference and educational and methodological material in the areas of retraining and advanced training, it is actively used by learners of the courses. Specialized departments are attached to the Centers for the implementation of pedagogical (qualification) practice.

The process of pedagogical practice includes attending classes at departments, holding open classes for learners. The analysis of the demonstrative lesson, conclusions, methodological materials, and the report on practice are discussed at the department meeting, assessed using a point system and formalized in the minutes. The practical implementation of such large-scale measures to further improve the system of retraining and advanced training of teaching staff at universities in Uzbekistan will be a great contribution to improving the quality of training highly qualified specialists.

Continuous education in our republic is one of the main sections of the National Program for Personnel Training, the basis for training qualified, competitive specialists, includes all types of education, state educational standards, components of the personnel training system and the content of their activities. The national education model of Uzbekistan is based on the concept of "Education for All Throughout Life". In this aspect, all links of the education system are involved in the formation of a comprehensively developed personality, predetermining the continuity and continuity in the development and enrichment of knowledge, skills and abilities at all stages of training and education of students. [3].

What does advanced training for teachers provide?

Continuous advanced training allows teachers to:

- Keep abreast of the latest changes in the field of education.
- Master new technologies and teaching methods.
- Improve the quality of their lessons. Find new approaches to working with students.

The benefits of the courses are as follows:

- Compliance of the teacher's qualifications with the established professional standard. ...
- Successful completion of certification to improve the qualification category or confirm it. ...
- Prospects for career growth. ...
- The opportunity to stay up to date with modern teaching methods.

[4].

Advanced training, as we wrote above, serves to improve knowledge and skills within the framework of an existing specialty. It allows you to confirm or expand competencies. Based on the results of such a program, students receive a certificate of advanced training, the validity of which is limited by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Digital technologies have become a cornerstone in the professional development and overall improvement of teaching staff quality. Here are some of the key ways digital tools contribute to this enhancement:

1. Access to Professional Development

- Online courses, webinars, and virtual workshops allow teachers to learn from global experts without geographical constraints.
- Platforms like Coursera, Udemy, and Khan Academy offer specialized training programs tailored to educators, fostering continuous learning.

2. Personalized Learning for Teachers

- Digital platforms provide adaptive learning paths, enabling teachers to focus on their specific areas of improvement.
- Data analytics from these platforms help educators track their progress and identify skill gaps.

3. Collaborative Platforms and Communities

- Digital tools like Google Workspace, Microsoft Teams, and Slack facilitate collaboration among teaching staff for lesson planning, resource sharing, and brainstorming.
- Online educator communities such as Edmodo and TeachMeet promote knowledge exchange and best practices sharing.

4. Innovative Teaching Techniques

- Teachers can experiment with cutting-edge methods such as gamification, flipped classrooms, and project-based learning, supported by tools like Kahoot, Quizizz, and Edmodo.
- Virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR) tools enhance classroom engagement and allow teachers to bring abstract concepts to life.

5. Efficient Administrative Tools

- Digital technologies simplify administrative tasks such as attendance tracking, grading, and feedback through Learning Management Systems (LMS) like Canvas, Moodle, or Blackboard.
- Automation frees up time for teachers to focus on pedagogy and student engagement.

6. Access to Global Resources

- Teachers can access an abundance of high-quality resources, including research papers, teaching guides, and multimedia materials, through platforms like Google Scholar and YouTube.
- Open educational resources (OER) make teaching content widely available, reducing costs and increasing accessibility.

7. Data-Driven Decision Making

- Analytics and reporting tools empower teachers to assess student performance and adjust teaching strategies effectively.
- Data visualization platforms help teachers better understand trends in classroom learning and improve outcomes.

8. Virtual Peer Observations and Feedback

- Teachers can record their lessons and receive feedback from peers or mentors, enabling constructive critiques and targeted improvements.
- Platforms like Sibme support video-based coaching and professional growth.

9. Globalization of Education

- Digital technologies enable teachers to connect with global peers and participate in cross-cultural collaborations, enriching their perspectives and teaching styles.

10. Encouraging Lifelong Learning

- Technologies such as podcasts, online libraries, and microlearning apps encourage teachers to remain updated with the latest trends, pedagogies, and subject knowledge.

Digital technologies are a catalyst for improving the quality of teaching staff by fostering innovation, collaboration, and personalized professional growth. By embracing these tools, educators can enhance their skills, better meet the needs of diverse learners, and stay ahead in a rapidly evolving educational landscape. [5].

Therefore, the goals of advanced training of administrative and pedagogical staff of higher educational institutions are to prepare each employee for the latest trends in professional development and technical progress. Another important goal of advanced training is to move up the career ladder.

REFERENCES

1. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated 21.06.2024 N PP-231 "On additional measures to improve the system of continuous professional development of employees of preschool and school education organizations". <https://nrm.uz/>
2. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of 11.07.2024 No. 415 "On measures for the effective organization of the system of retraining and advanced training of managers and teachers of higher education organizations." <https://www.norma.uz>
3. Мирзиёев Ш.М. Критический анализ, жесткая дисциплина и персональная ответственность должны стать повседневной нормой в деятельности каждого руководителя. Т.: Узбекистан, 2017. 103 с.
4. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should become the daily norm in the activities of every leader. Т.: Uzbekistan, 2017. 103 p.
5. Anarkulova G.M. Model of training teachers of vocational education based on a systems approach. Scientific journal "Young scientist". No. 13 (93). July., 2019. 590-592. Pages 93-96.